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Contents

Research Article

**Identification of the Adaptation Strategies to Mitigate Flash
Flood Risk in Sri Lanka – Case Study in Ja-Ela**

*W A U D Perera, N K N M Nakkawita, H P A M Siriwardana, R S
M Samarasekara*

**Growth and Yield Performances of Cabbage Grown under a
Protected House in Low Country Wet Zone of Sri Lanka as
Affected by Artificial Lights and Rate of Albert Fertilizer**

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Kumarasinghe, M K D K Piyaratne*

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